

Disproof of Collatz Conjecture by using O-notation

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ABSTRACT

We give the full disproof of Collatz conjecture using bit-O operational logic.

Keywords: O-notation, Collatz function, disproof.

INTRODUCTION

The attempt to solve this problem was done by Akram Louiz in his work [1], since many times the conjecture was unproven [2, 3] – indeed, the big-O notation [4, 5] used to estimate the algorithm notation now can be used in theorem proving despite the relation between complexity classes.

DISPROOF

Let's assume the following for Collatz function $f(n)$:

$$O(f(n))=n^k.$$

Let's give the case of number 2^m , where m is arbitrary and as big as any integer number, then we have:

$$O(f(n))=O(f(2^m))=m.$$

Let's consider another case where the number has least number of power of two, $2^m - 1$:

$$O(f(n))=O(f(2^m-1))\approx O(3^m)\neq O(n^k).$$

The above statement is a contradiction, thus:

$$O(f(n))\neq n^k \Rightarrow f(n) \in NP.$$

CONCLUSION

It follows that Collatz function is in non-polynomial class, which is a contradiction as only polynomial functions can be approximated to the given value.

REFERENCES

1. Louiz, Akram. (2025). A mathematical letter that disproves by contradiction the Collatz conjecture. 10.13140/RG.2.2.28997.56802.
2. Van Bendegem, J. P. (2005). The Collatz conjecture. A case study in mathematical problem solving. *Logic and Logical Philosophy*, 14(1), 7-23.
3. Chen, C. (2025). Proof of the Collatz Conjecture. *Academic Journal of Mathematical Sciences*, 6(1), 27-44.
4. Chivers, I., Sleightholme, J., Chivers, I., & Sleightholme, J. (2015). An introduction to Algorithms and the Big O Notation. *Introduction to Programming with Fortran: With Coverage of Fortran 90, 95, 2003, 2008 and 77*, 359-364.
5. Rutanen, K. (2016). O-notation in Algorithm Analysis.